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A MODEL FOR INNOVATIVE HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT TECHNOLOGIES IMPLEMENTATION INTO THE CIVIL SERVICE OF UKRAINE

МОДЕЛЬ ВПРОВАДЖЕННЯ ІННОВАЦІЙНИХ ТЕХНОЛОГІЙ УПРАВЛІННЯ ЛЮДСЬКИМИ РЕСУРСАМИ В ДЕРЖАВНІЙ СЛУЖБІ УКРАЇНИ

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Балан О.С., Шепель М.Є. Модель впровадження інноваційних технологій управління людськими ресурсами в державній службі України. Науково-методична стаття.

Зміни в системі державного управління зумовлюють необхідність удосконалення системи державної служби, формування нової кадрової політики, що базується на якісних управлінських стандартах та врахуванні інноваційних технологій управління персоналом. Мета статті запропонувати модель впровадження інноваційних технологій управління людськими ресурсами на державній службі України. Авторами зроблено аналіз дослідження управління людськими ресурсами у науково-дослідній літературі. Наведено статистичні дані щодо цінностей державних службовців, організаційної культури, позицій державних службовців щодо покращення сфери управління людськими ресурсами. Мета запропонованої моделі – шляхи впровадження інноваційних технологій управління людськими ресурсами в державній службі; результат – удосконалення управління людськими ресурсами на державній службі завдяки інноваційним технологіям.

Ключові слова: модель, інноваційні технології, управління людськими ресурсами, державна служба

Balan O.S., Shepel M.Ye. A Model for Innovative Human Resource Management Technologies Implementation into the Civil Service of Ukraine. Scientific and methodical article.

Changes in the system of public administration necessitate improvement of the civil service system, a new personnel policy formation based on high-quality management standards and consideration of innovative human resource management technologies. The aim of the article is to propose a model for innovative human resource management (HRM) technologies implementation in the civil service of Ukraine. The authors analyse the research on HRM in the scientific and research literature. The article provides statistical data on the civil servants' values, organisational culture, and positions of civil servants on improving human resource management. The aim of the proposed model is to introduce the ways for innovative HRM technologies implementation in the civil service; the result is improved HRM in the civil service via innovative technologies.

Keywords: model, innovative technologies, human resource management (HRM), civil service

One of the main factors of Ukraine's competitiveness and indicators of economic integration and political association with the European Union is the effectiveness of public administration reform and forming a proper system of public management and administration. Changes in the public administration system necessitate improving the civil service system, forming a new personnel policy based on high-quality management standards and consideration of innovative HRM technologies.

In 2015, the Law of Ukraine "On Civil Service" [1] and many regulations were adopted. This drastically changed the institution of civil service and approaches to the personnel management processes organisation in the civil service system. The State Administration Reform Strategy of Ukraine for 2022-2025 notes that, according to European principles, the civil service should be professional, honest, politically neutral, based on achievements, and also be citizen-oriented [2].

The problem relevance regarding the organisation of an effective HRM system in the civil service is due to the Russian Federation's full-scale invasion, as well as introducing martial law throughout the territory of Ukraine. The state has prioritized preserving human potential, using all possible means and methods for this.

Analysis of recent research and publications

The following researchers dedicated their works to the issues of HRM: O. Beryslavska, V. Ivanov, I. Lavryk, T. Zbrytska, H. Savchenko, M. Tatarevska, N. Yakymenko-Tereshchenko, L. Kozhurina, O. Krushelnytska, D. Melnychu, T. Balanovska M. Mykhailichenko, A. Troian, K. Kozak, Yu. Ruban, N. Bazaliiska, I. Prodius, A. Borova, N. Iziumtseva, A. Kulinska, D. Kostyuk, K. Topalova, L. Chernyshova, I. Borysenko; the HRM phenomenon in the civil service was studied by: M. Kanavets, N. Dragomyretska, I. Klymenko, L. Prokopenko, I. Matvieienko,

D. Samofalov, O. Bahrim, V. Bakumenko, S. Popov, O. Amosov, N. Havkalova, M. Izha, N. Horncharuk, L. Prudyus, A. Hryshchuk, D. Balukh, V. Melnyk, S. Selivanov, A. Kashlakova, S. Serohin, Ye. Borodin, K. Komarova, N. Lypovska, T. Tarasenko, N. Aliushyna; modern trends in HRM in the civil service and the priority directions of innovative technologies implementation in the civil service of Ukraine were studied by: N. Honcharuk, Yu. Pyrohova, S. Sardak, Yu. Kizilov, O. Parkhomenko-Kutsevil, O. Shevchuk, M. Kovtun, V. Spasenko, I. Matvieienko, H. Panchenko, A. Kulinska, K. Kuznietsova, I. Rozputenko, O. Pukhkal, O. Braichenko, N. Obushna, T. Vasylevska, O. Matviienko, M. Tsyvin, O. Lihonenko, I. Tsymbaliuk, O. Demchenko.

These and other scholars have formed a solid methodological ground for studying various aspects of HRM in the civil service system.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

At the same time, it should be noted that the proposals of certain directions regarding this process optimisation, as well as the theoretical and applied aspects of personnel potential management in the civil service of Ukraine, have not yet been sufficiently studied.

The aim of the article is to propose the model for innovative HRM technologies implementation in the civil service of Ukraine.

The main part

The concept of "human resources" is a key in describing the qualitative and significant aspects of personnel management in public authorities. It includes such components as of public service development, organisational culture, ethics and moral authority, incorruptibility, as well as team relations improvement, mutual responsibility, stimulation, motivation and others.

Regarding the concept of "HRM in the civil service", it should be understood as selection, planning, development, evaluation, rational use, motivation and reward, career planning, and all management functions implementation related to increasing the human resource potential in public institutions [3].

Many researchers believe that the following aspects should be included in the HRM responsibilities: providing state institutions with qualified and morally

stable personnel; processes analysis of personnel selection, placement, maintenance and professional training; measures development to improve personnel activities; introducing modern personnel management methods; studying civil servants' professional and moral qualities and creating personnel reserves personnel needs planning of institutions; and support in solving social and everyday problems of civil servants related to the provision of legally defined benefits [4].

The HRM system includes the following key elements: an expert group on management equipment; information infrastructure for personnel management; a set of technical means of the control system; a set of methods and methodological approaches to labour organisation and personnel management; regulatory framework; a set of management programmes [5].

One of the main goals of the "Strategy for the Reform of Public Administration of Ukraine for 2022-2025" [2] is the effective HRN services formation in state institutions, by increasing their capabilities to establish and develop modern HRM in coordination with the National Agency of Ukraine on Civil Service (NAUCS) [6]. The capacity of the HRM service means its ability to perform its tasks, functions and achieve its goals independently or with the help of cooperation with relevant structural units and institutions.

To date, the success of management is related to the development and implementation of mechanisms that ensure the effectiveness of civil servants' activity. It is important to look for new ways, forms and learning methods for them. In this context, it is recommended to create and implement educational and training programmes that cover theoretical and practical aspects of professional competence and prepare strategic managers who can manage effectively in conditions of external and internal risks [7].

In modern conditions, the main tasks of HRM in the civil service are the prediction and planning of HR needs; formation of a staff team; selection and placement of employees; effective use of labour force; personnel training and professional development; and the introducing technological innovations into the personnel process. For greater clarity, we will present the tasks of human resource management in the civil service in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Tasks of HRM in the Civil Service
Source: compiled by authors on materials [8]

Ukraine implements the state HR policy through the systematic organisation of work with personnel, in particular with managers, which is defined as one of the main functions of HRM. HRM in civil service should be effectively used to achieve the planned goals of the development of national and regional communities [9].

The literature analysis on HRM of the civil service has revealed that the main functions of the civil service personnel management system are the following: professional (aimed at forming the employees'

professional composition); systemic and planned (includes personnel technology and personnel planning methods); efficiency function (achieving the best results at minimum costs); scientific (based on scientific research and development); function of continuity (a unified personnel policy implementation), hierarchical (functions distribution between human resource management units); operative (timely execution and implementation of decisions) and perspective (directed to future development) (Table 1).

Table 1. Functions of the HRM system in the civil service

Functions	Essence
Professional	It is focused on the formation of a professional staff of civil servants
Systematic and planned	They cover the activities of personnel technology, the entire range of methods of personnel planning
Efficiency	Certifies the best results at the lowest costs
Scientific	It is based on scientific activity and developments
Continuities	Implementing a unified personnel policy
Hierarchical	Narrowing between different units of personnel management
Operative	Timeliness of adoption and implementation
Promising	Orientation to further development

Source: compiled by authors on materials [10]

With the entry into force of the Law of Ukraine "On Civil Service", there was a need to strengthen the strategic role of the HRM service in the state administrative system. This service is responsible for carrying out management processes in state bodies, including personnel selection, planning and organisation of measures to improve the level of civil servants' professional competence, as well as for documenting their recruitment, completion of service and dismissal [11].

It should be noted that during the period of martial law, in accordance with the Law of Ukraine "On the Legal Regime of Martial Law" dated 12 May 2015, No. 28, appointments to civil service positions take place without competitive selection [12].

Successful administrative reform depends on the quality of HRM in public institutions. The issue of the functioning of these structural divisions is one of the main aspects for the modernisation of the civil service and personnel management in public bodies. In the context of implementing the administrative transformations in Ukraine, an important task is the civil service system adaptation to the best international standards and practices. Therefore, a necessary element is introducing and applying innovative approaches in human resource management in civil service.

Introducing innovative technologies in HRM will create a stable civil service independent of political influences in Ukraine. This service will have a high level of professionalism and the ability to effectively solve the task of formulating state policy in the field of social and economic development.

Starting from 2019, the National Agency of Ukraine on Civil Service conducts an annual survey as part of the "Civil Service Feedback" initiative. These

survey results show key values and psychological aspects in civil service, such as professionalism, service, responsibility, cooperation, efficiency, integrity, diligence, and stress resistance [13].

The process of civil service professionalisation also covers the motivation system, which is currently undergoing reformation in the period from 2021 to 2023. This includes a system of remuneration based on the grading of civil service positions, a fair assessment of achievements (horizontal career growth without changing the position, based on the results of professional training, etc.), which allows to ensure a level of remuneration comparable to the market [14].

Civil service professionalisation in Ukraine, which in the general context of professional training (systemic activity) was transformed into professional development through the statutory provision on mandatory credits, did not meet the expectations set for it. In 2020, as part of the implementation of the Public Administration Reform Strategy (No. 474 of 24 June 2016), the NAUCS conducted a series of studies "Civil Service in Ukraine: Your Point of View" with the support of the Centre for Integrity in Defence (CID, Norway), the State Institution "Institute for Economics and Forecasting of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine" (Civil Service Feedback Cycle) [13].

The results of these studies point to the key civil servants' values, such as professionalism, responsibility, teamwork, efficiency, honesty and integrity. Studies show that universal human values, such as respect for human dignity, rights and freedoms, benevolence, impartiality, and equality (25.0%), have significantly lost priority in the central bodies of executive power, in favour of the priorities of "serving the state", public interests (31.3%) and conscientiousness/diligence (27%) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. The Civil Servants' Values
Source: compiled by authors on materials [13]

In 8 months of 2021, only 24,000 officials received advanced training compared to 86,000 in the previous period (a decrease from 43% to 22%). According to NAUCS data [15], in the period from 2019 to 2021, 1,870 deputies of local councils attended professional training courses out of a total of 42,560. With the introduction of the Knowledge Management Portal,

2,500 out of 35,000 officials applied for the courses posted on the portal. This information indicates the improper implementation of the provisions of the Law of Ukraine "On Service in Local Self-Government Bodies" [15] regarding the mandatory training of elected officials of local self-government as a professional duty and responsibility (Table 2).

Table 2. Improving the Civil Servants' Qualifications

Period	Characteristics
8 months of 2021	Only 24,000 officials upgraded their qualifications
The previous period	86 thousand (decrease from 43% to 22%)
In the period from 2019 to 2021	professional training courses were attended by 1,870 deputies of local councils out of a total of 42,560

Source: compiled by authors on materials [15]

With the beginning of a full-scale invasion, the need for the civil service of Ukraine for dedicated highly qualified specialists, who are capable of independent flexible thinking and finding solutions for complex management tasks, became more urgent.

The results of "The Impact of War on Approaches to Human Capital Management" survey conducted by

Deloitte in Ukraine and the American Chamber of Commerce [16] in Ukraine during the war in June 2022 showed the civil servants' positions on improving in the field of HRM: the need to improve management workload (57.0%); feasibility of real-time support and assistance (57.0%); the importance of reviewing the organizational structure (49.0%). (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. The Civil Servants' Positions Regarding the HRM Improvement
Source: compiled by authors on materials [16]

Also, creating the well-being system as a support for productive replenishment, career realisation, financial support, health care, psychological stability, and social demand [16] occupies an important place.

Corporate culture is of great importance in modern human resource management trends. According to the "Research on the Organizational Culture of the Civil Service of Ukraine", the majority (62.0%) of the

surveyed civil servants of central executive bodies consider the corporate culture of their state body to be conducive to professional development and achievement of results. At the same time, 20.3% of the respondents believe that the corporate culture in their state bodies leads to frequent conflicts and hinders professional development and achievement of results (Table 3).

Table 3. The Civil Servants' of The Organizational (Corporate) Culture Evaluation by the Civil Servants in Their Public Body (among the Surveyed Civil servants of Central Executive bodies)

A. Very favourable (contributes to professional development and achievement of results)		B. Very toxic (leads to frequent conflicts and hinders professional development and achievement of results)		
I completely agree with the statement A	I rather agree with the statement A	I disagree with the statements A and B	I rather agree with the statement B	I Completely agree with the statement B
32.8%	29.2%	17.7%	11.2%	9.1%
62.0%			20.3%	

Source: compiled by authors on materials [13]

The majority (57.5%) of the surveyed civil servants of local authorities consider the corporate culture of their state body to be conducive to professional development and achievement of results.

Meanwhile, almost every sixth respondent (15.4%) believes that the corporate culture in their state bodies leads to the frequency of conflicts and makes it difficult for professional development and achievement of results (Table 4).

Table 4. The Civil Servants' of The Organizational (Corporate) Culture Evaluation by the Civil Servants in Their Public Body (Among the Surveyed Civil Servants of Local Executive Bodies)

Very toxic (leads to frequent conflicts and hinders professional development and achievement results) 100 points	90	80	70	60	50	40	30	20	Very favorable (contributes to professional development and achievement results) 1 point
4.3%	2.3%	3.7%	5.1%	8.3%	18.6%	14.9%	15.2%	11.7%	15.9%

Source: compiled by authors on materials [13]

As we can see from Table 4, the majority of civil servants of local authorities tend to have a favourable corporate culture.

The surveyed civil servants of central executive bodies believe that the greatest responsibility for the organizational culture formation rests with the head of the public body (75.6%), with themselves (69.1%) and with the human resource management service (59.3%). The civil servants of the "B" category and those civil servants who have been working in this authority for 11 years – 20 years old, highly appreciate their own responsibility.

Digitisation has become another direction in HRM.

The HRM digitisation of the civil service of Ukraine to transform the personnel management process may include the following measures: personnel management processes automation, using integrated mobile applications, data analysis in the field of human resource management and using large volumes of data (Big Data), implementation of virtual reality (VR) and artificial intelligence technologies. etc.

The process of HRM digital transformation in the civil service of Ukraine has already started. Back in 2019, the National Agency of Ukraine on Civil Service (NAUCS) identified as its mission the creation of a personnel management function in the Ukrainian civil service. The NAUCS strategy focused on strengthening the authorities by attracting new management, creating the HRM function and cultural transformations within the organisation, as well as the

maximum implementation of digital tools to optimise old mechanical processes [17].

In the field of digitisation, among the main achievements of NAUCS in 2019 were: the transfer of HR processes to electronic form – the creation of a HELP DESK for candidates, Career.gov.ua, Careerbot, the integration of the Career.gov.ua civil service job portal with Work.ua and Robota.ua; ensuring proper conditions for the professional development of civil servants and local self-government officials (the Knowledge Management Portal was launched), strengthening the institutional capacity of the NAUCS [17].

Nowadays, under the conditions of the Russian Federation's full-scale invasion, the development of a model for innovative HRM technologies implementation in the civil service of Ukraine is of great importance.

The aim of the model is to introduce the ways of innovative HRM technologies implementation in the civil service of Ukraine. We will present our model in the form of a block scheme, which includes the following components: strategic innovative planning; analysis of needs and opportunities; involving management and of stakeholders' support; using innovative technologies in the human resource management of the civil service; using talent management in HRM in the civil service; personnel training and development; change management and adaptation. For greater clarity, we will present our model in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The Model for Innovative HRM Technologies Implementation in the Civil Service

Source: the authors' own elaboration

The basic principles of the HR strategy in the overall strategic planning system are as follows: the organisation will contribute to society and adhere to the principle of legality in matters of human resource policy; information about all vacant positions will be communicated to the staff; all positions will be distributed only on merit; no organisational change can be implemented without careful discussion with those who may be directly affected; remuneration will be similar to the best indicators in the industry; staff will participate in the process of HR management [18]. The objectives of strategic HR planning are: 1) formulation of the general strategy and the strategy of human resource management (functional strategy); 2) development of strategic, tactical and operational goals; 3) development of plans for implementation of strategic, tactical and operational goals [19].

The next element of the model is the analysis of needs and opportunities. Thus, the assessment of needs and opportunities in the context of the civil service will help identify specific problems and opportunities for the innovative technologies introduction. For example, the needs for staff development include increased value of highly qualified specialists; guaranteed employment, prospects for the formation and implementation of a career path; high adaptability and maximum preparation of staff for promising tasks; motivation and job satisfaction, the ability to identify promising employees, the formation of a high-quality and efficient personnel reserve; use of advanced technologies, rapid response of qualified personnel to changes in the environment and customer needs; increased efficiency [20].

The support of management and other stakeholders is important for the successful implementation of

innovations. Management can play a key role in creating a culture that fosters innovation by empowering employees to experiment and contribute new ideas. They can also provide the necessary resources and support to develop and implement these ideas. Other stakeholders, such as employees, customers, and partners, can also contribute significantly to the innovation process. Their experiences and perspectives can help identify new opportunities for improvement and they can be important agents of change in implementing new ideas. Therefore, for the successful implementation of innovations in HRM in the public service, it is important to ensure the active support and participation of all stakeholders.

Let's consider the main HR technologies and their impact on the human resources management system in the civil service (Table 5).

Talent management is an important tool of HRM, especially in the civil service¹. This is a new direction in HR management, which is aimed at identifying and developing talented personnel in order to increase the efficiency, effectiveness and quality of the organization's activities [21].

Using talent management allows to ensure the growth of motivation for work, loyalty to companies, increase of creativity and self-realisation. It includes such components as HR branding and selection, mentoring, coaching, evaluation, performance management, talent development and retention [22].

In conditions of uncertainty, it is important to consider innovative global HR practices in this area. This is especially true of the civil service, where it is important to attract and retain talented employees [21].

Table 5. Using Innovative Technologies in HRM in the Civil Service

Technology	Function
HR processes automation due to mobile applications	This integration allows quickly and conveniently plan work meetings, set tasks, communicate in work chats, engage in online training and professional development at a convenient time
Active use of cloud services	The need to work with large amounts of data takes a lot of time and effort. Cloud services help with solving many issues related to information processing: they speed up the search and processing of information, and optimise its storage. An equally important function of cloud services is high information security, which guarantees confidentiality and protects the company from the loss of important information
Predictive HR analytics and Big Data	Using HR analytics makes it possible to predict development scenarios based on the analysis of large volumes of data and simplifies management decision-making
Applying augmented reality (VR technologies).	Innovative VR technologies make it possible to diversify the process of personnel training and development to facilitate the employees' adaptation in the organisation. The latest technologies of augmented reality are able to create conditions for receiving a unique and diverse experience that will increase the interest of the staff and stimulate the improvement of work efficiency
Applying artificial intelligence (AI) technologies.	AI is able to facilitate the work of the HR manager, depending on the needs for which it is applied. AI technologies can be successfully used in recruiting, career advancement, training and development of personnel

Source: compiled by authors on materials [19]

Training and development of the civil service personnel in Ukraine is carried out through the system of educational institutions, institutions, and organizations that have the right to provide relevant educational services. Professional training of civil servants, heads of local state administrations, their first deputies and deputies, officials of local self-government ensures the appropriate level of their professional qualifications for their professional activities [23]. The training programme for the civil servants who hold civil service positions of the "B" category (at least once every three years) is aimed at deepening and expanding the participants' understanding of the public administration system and their own role in it [24].

An important role in the development and consolidation of digital competences is played by the system of forming and placing a state order for training and upgrading the civil servants and local self-government officials' qualifications [25].

Training and development of the civil service personnel are important components of effective HR management. They contribute to improving professional qualifications, developing competencies and ensure a high level of performance of assigned tasks. It is important to note that civil service personnel have the necessary skills to use innovative technologies. This may include conducting trainings, developing instructions and self-study materials.

The Center for the Adaptation of the Civil Service to the EU Standards is working on improving the

human resources management system in the civil service. This includes the implementation of HR management system based on the competency approach, the development of strategic documents on the human resource management in the civil service, and the improvement of the level of professional competence of civil servants [26].

It is important to emphasise that in order to create a professional, politically neutral, honest and effective public service, in addition to improving the legislative framework for HRM, it is important to develop institutional capacity and ensure consistency in the implementation of new principles of human resource management services [27].

Conclusion

Introducing innovative technologies may require changes in organisational culture and work processes. It is necessary to have change management strategies and ensure personnel adaptation to new conditions. The main directions of improving HRM in the field of civil service of Ukraine include the modernisation of civil service and HRM in public authorities. It is important to note that outdated forms, methods and technologies of HRM are preserved in the civil service.

In order to create a professional, politically neutral, honest and effective public service, in addition to improving the legal provision of human resource management, it is important to develop institutional capacity and ensure consistency in the new principles implementation of HRM services.

Abstract

One of the main factors of Ukraine's competitiveness and indicators of economic integration and political association with the European Union is the effectiveness of public administration reform and forming a proper system of public management and administration. Changes in the public administration system necessitate improving the civil service system, forming a new personnel policy based on high-quality management standards and consideration of innovative HR management technologies.

The problem relevance regarding the organisation of an effective HRM system in the civil service is due to the Russian Federation's full-scale invasion, as well as introducing martial law throughout the territory of Ukraine. The state has made it a priority to preserve human potential, using all possible means and methods for this.

The aim of the article is to propose the model for innovative HRM technologies implementation in the civil service of Ukraine.

The authors analyse the research on human resource management in the scientific and research literature. The article provides statistical data on the civil servants' values, organisational culture, and positions of civil servants on improving human resource management

The aim of the model is to identify the ways of innovative HRM technologies introduction in the civil service. The model is presented as a block scheme, which includes the following components: strategic innovative planning; analysis of needs and opportunities; involving management and of stakeholders' support; using innovative technologies in the human resource management of civil service; using talent management in the human resource management in civil service; personnel training and development; change management and adaptation. The result of the model is improved human resource management in the civil service via innovative technologies.

Innovative technologies implementation necessitates adjustments in organisational culture and work processes, requiring effective change management strategies and the facilitation of personnel adaptation to new conditions. Key areas for enhancing human resources management within Ukraine's civil service sector include the modernisation of public service operations and HR management within state institutions. It is crucial to address the persistence of outdated practices, methods, and technologies in personnel management. To establish a professional, politically neutral, honest, and efficient public service, alongside enhancing the legal framework for HR management, it is essential to develop institutional capacity and ensure the consistent application of new personnel management principles.

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